

Original Research

Reproductive Performance and Catecholamine Responses in Yankasa Rams Supplemented with Synthetic Selenium and Vitamin E in a Semi-arid Environment of Nigeria

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Received: 17 July 2025; Accepted: 07 September 2025; Published online: 25 September 2025

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Doi: 10.5281/zenodo.16748568

Ark:/31129/11x16748568

ABSTRACT

This study investigated the effects of selenium (Se) and vitamin E (Vit. E) supplementation on testicular traits, sperm morphology, and catecholamine responses in Yankasa rams. Sixteen yearling rams (22.5 ± 2.1 kg) were randomly assigned to four treatments and monitored for 9 weeks in a completely randomized design: Control (no supplementation), Se (0.6 mg), Se + Vit. E (0.6 mg Se + 2 g Vit. E), and Vit. E (2 g). Results showed that testicular characteristics were significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher in the selenium-supplemented group as compared to others. However, the Se + Vit. E group showed significantly lower testicular weights. The various spermatozoa characteristics measured differ significantly ($p < 0.05$) across the treatment groups except for normal, bent tail, and detached head. The percentage of spermatozoa with proximal droplets was significantly ($p < 0.05$) lower in the Se + Vit. E group compared to others. Microcephalic sperm was absent in treated animals but present in the control ($1.5 \pm 0.1\%$) ($P=0.019$). Catecholamine analysis showed that dopamine was higher ($P < 0.05$) in the Se + vit. E group as compared with rams in the control and Vit. E groups. Adrenaline (0.45 ± 0.05) and noradrenaline (0.163 ± 0.11) were significantly lower in vitamin E as compared to other treatments. These results indicate that Se alone enhances testicular development, while Se + Vit. E improves sperm quality. However, animals receiving supplements had reduced catecholamine secretion (adrenaline and noradrenaline).

KEYWORDS: Catecholamine, reproductive performance, selenium, vitamin E, Yankasa rams

INTRODUCTION

Small ruminants, particularly sheep, are vital to sustainable farming systems in arid and semi-arid regions, where they support livelihoods and food security (Rjili et al., 2023). However, environmental stressors such as rising temperatures, feed scarcity, and stress increasingly threaten their productivity and reproductive efficiency (Chauhan et al., 2016). Climate

projections indicate a global temperature increase of $1.5\text{--}6.5^\circ\text{C}$ by 2050, further exacerbating these challenges (Sylla et al., 2016). In such conditions, the role of antioxidants like selenium (Se) and vitamin E (Vit. E) becomes critical in mitigating oxidative damage and enhancing reproductive performance in ruminants (Barcelos et al., 2022).

Selenium, an essential component of antioxidant enzymes such as glutathione peroxidase, plays a key role in protecting cellular membranes and supporting spermatogenesis (Ahsan et al., 2014). Similarly, vitamin E, a potent lipid-soluble antioxidant, prevents lipid peroxidation and maintains sperm membrane integrity (Alhidary et al., 2015). While the individual benefits of Se and Vit. E are well-documented in some livestock species, their combined effects on testicular development, epididymal function, and sperm quality in Yankasa rams remain insufficiently explored. Existing studies report conflicting results, with some indicating synergistic improvements in reproductive metrics (Elbaz and Razek, 2019), while others suggest no significant benefits (Mahmoud et al., 2013). This discrepancy highlights the need for targeted research to optimize supplementation strategies for this breed, particularly in tropical environments where heat stress and nutritional limitations are prevalent.

Catecholamines, including adrenaline, noradrenaline, and dopamine, play a fundamental role in the regulation of reproductive physiology in mammals. Beyond their function as stress biomarkers, they influence testicular blood flow, steroidogenesis, and sperm transport through the epididymis (Frungieri and Mayerhofer, 2024; Urra et al., 2014). Stress-induced alterations in catecholamine secretion can disrupt the hypothalamic–pituitary–gonadal (HPG) axis, impair gonadotropin release, and reduce testosterone synthesis, thereby compromising spermatogenesis and libido (Demirtaş et al., 2018). Moreover, elevated oxidative stress has been associated with increased catecholamine levels, creating a feedback loop that aggravates reproductive dysfunction (Guerriero et al., 2018). Hence, evaluating catecholamine responses alongside testicular and sperm parameters provides a better understanding of how antioxidants such as Se and Vit. E may mitigate stress-related reproductive impairments in rams.

The Yankasa sheep, a key breed in West African livestock systems, is prized for its adaptability but faces productivity constraints due to oxidative stress and poor reproductive management. Enhancing ram fertility through nutritional interventions could significantly improve flock productivity and genetic potential. Despite evidence supporting the role of Se and Vit. E in

male reproduction, specific data on their effects in Yankasa rams (particularly on testicular morphology, sperm abnormalities, and stress biomarkers) are lacking. Addressing this gap is essential for developing practical, cost-effective strategies for smallholder farmers. This study evaluated the effects of Se and Vit. E supplementation on testicular characteristics, sperm morphology, and catecholamine levels in Yankasa rams. By examining these parameters, we aimed to clarify the potential of these antioxidants to enhance reproductive performance under stress-prone conditions.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Experimental site

The study was carried out at the Department of Animal Science, Livestock Teaching and Research Farm, Main Campus, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, located between latitudes 13°06'58"N and 13°07'24"N and longitudes 5°15'03"E and 5°15'38"E in the northern part of Nigeria (Akinbiyi et al., 2019) and at an altitude of 292 m above sea level (Nakakana et al., 2020). The state falls within the Sudan savannah vegetation zone with alternating short and dry seasons. The hot dry spell extends from March to May and sometimes to June in the extreme northern part. A short, cool, dry period (harmattan) occurs between October and February (Balarabe et al., 2015). The annual rainfall is about 500 mm, and the rainy season extends from mid-May to September, while the dry season lasts for more than 7 months, starting in November and continuing until April of the following year (Akinbiyi et al., 2019). A maximum temperature of 41°C has been reported in April and a minimum of 12°C in January (Shiru et al., 2020). The state is one of the largest livestock-producing areas in Nigeria.

Experimental Animals and their Management

Sixteen (16) yearling Yankasa rams with an average body weight (BW) of 22.5 ± 2.14 kg and similar morphological development were used for this study. The experimental animals were sourced from livestock market within Sokoto State. The animals were dewormed with Ivermectin 5% (1 ml/50 kg liveweight) and Albendazole (10 ml/50 kg liveweight) against external and internal parasites, respectively, before the

commencement of the experiment. Also, oxytetracycline (a broad-spectrum antibiotic) and multivitamin injections were given at a rate of 1 ml/10 kg body weight for three days to suppress any subclinical infections and to reduce stress, respectively. Feed and water were given to the animal ad libitum. The animals were individually housed in pens (2 m² per animal) with adequate ventilation. An experimental diet was offered according to the National Research Council (NRC, 2007) for the specie as a complete feed ration (CFR). The animals were quarantined for 2 weeks, during which wheat offal and cowpea husk were provided ad libitum.

Treatments and Experimental Design

The experiment was conducted in a Completely Randomized Design (CRD) with four treatments and four replications. The animals were acclimatized to their microclimate for 14 days and provided with feed and water. All the animals received the experimental diet (Table 1) *ad libitum*. Apart from T₀, which was the control (no supplementation), treated groups received the experimental diet plus a daily consumption of 0.6 mg selenium (T₁), 0.6 mg selenium + 2 g vitamin E (T₂), and 2 g vitamin E (T₃).

The company Shaanxi Bieyouth Biotech Co. Ltd. (China) supplied the supplement agents selenium (sodium selenite) and vitamin E (alpha-tocopherol acetate) that were given to animals via wheat offal as a carrier at 50 g/head/day. The feeding trial lasted for 9 weeks (63 days), during which carriers were mixed biweekly to minimize oxidation of vitamin E.

DATA COLLECTION

Testicular-epididymal measurements

The epididymis from each testis was carefully removed using a scalpel (Dadashpour et al., 2022). Testicles were weighed on a sensitive balance scale (0.01 g, Model: WT10002G, WANT Balance Instrument Co., Ltd., China). The length, width, and diameter of testicles and epididymal length were measured with a flexible measuring tape (Yahaya et al., 2017).

Table 1: Composition of experimental diet fed to Yankasa rams

Ingredients (kg)	Percentage
Groundnut haulm	10
Soybean meal	10
Cottonseed cake	20
Rice offal	3
Wheat offal	30
Cowpea husk	10
Maize Bran	18.5
Salt	0.5
Total	100
Calculated Chemical Composition	
Energy (Kcal/Kg ME)	2327
Crude Protein (% DM)	18.95
Crude Fiber (% DM)	16.75
Crude Fat (% DM)	2.5

DM: dry matter; ME: Metabolizable Energy

Spermatozoa recovery

The scrotum containing the testicles was removed and taken to the laboratory in aseptic medium. spermatozoa were collected by testicle harvest. All glassware for collection and handling was cleaned and sterilized using high-pressure steam, dried, and warmed at 35°C. After collection, the tube was immediately placed in a water bath at 37°C. The spermatozoa were collected by the flushing method. Briefly, a cut was made near the corpus and the proximal side that separated each cauda epididymis. Then, the caudal epididymis was injected with 3-5 ml of normal saline using a blunted 23G needle. After that, several longitudinal incisions were made and kept in a 100-mm Petri dish for 15 min in a water bath at 37°C (Hasani Al-Ameri, 2022), as adopted from Dadashpour et al. (2022). Finally, the spermatozoa were harvested in a glass tube from the Petri dishes as an exudate from the epididymis.

Spermatozoa quality characteristics

Morphological Evaluation: On a labeled clean frosted slide, 10 µL of well-mixed aliquot containing spermatozoa is added on one end of the slide. A second slide is used with an angle of 45° to quickly spread the drop along the frosted slide, forming a smooth and even smear. The slides are prepared in duplicate and then air-dried before staining (Agarwal et al., 2022). The Diff-Quik set is used in staining the smear as described by

Agarwal et al. (2016). Indeed, after drying, a few drops of the mounting medium Cytoseal are placed on the slide and covered with a coverslip. The slide is allowed to dry completely before it is examined under a bright field microscope (**Agarwal et al., 2016**). Microscopic examination was carried out using a bright-field binocular microscope (Olympus CX23, Olympus Corporation, Tokyo, Japan) under oil immersion at 1000× magnification. For each slide, a minimum of 200 spermatozoa were counted, and the percentages of morphologically normal spermatozoa and those with abnormalities (bent tail, detached head, proximal droplet, coiled tail, and microcephalic conditions) were recorded.

Catecholamine (dopamine, adrenaline, noradrenalin) determination

The catecholamines were analyzed using a competitive assay (kit CatCombi ELISA, IBL Laboratorios Inmunobiológicos, Hamburg, Germany): (RE 592 51) for the measures of adrenaline (A) and (RE 592 61) for noradrenaline (NA) (**Shi et al., 2022**). The sensitivity in the analyses was 10 pg/ml for A and 20 pg/ml for NA. Plasma dopamine concentrations were determined using the radioenzymatic method described by **Johnson et al. (1980)**. In this procedure, dopamine in plasma was enzymatically O-methylated by catechol-O-methyltransferase (COMT) in the presence of tritiated S-adenosylmethionine ($^3\text{H-SAM}$), producing radiolabeled O-methylated metabolites. The resulting radioactivity was quantified with a Packard Tri-Carb liquid scintillation spectrometer in the ^3H channel.

Blood sample collection

Approximately 5 mL of blood samples was collected from the jugular vein of each animal and was transferred to a vacutainer for serum preparation. Centrifugation was done at 3000 rpm for 15 min for serum separation.

Data analysis

Data generated from the experiment were submitted to analysis of variance using Statistical Analysis System-SAS Institute (2004) version 9.4 (SAS Institute Inc.,

Cary, NC, USA). Least significant difference (LSD) was used to separate the means at the 5% level of significance.

RESULTS

Effects of selenium and vitamin E supplementation on testicular characteristics of Yankasa rams

Table 2 presents the effects of selenium (Se) and vitamin E supplementation on the testicular characteristics of Yankasa rams. All parameters measured are significantly different ($p < 0.05$) across the treatments except for vas deferens length and testicular breadth. Testicular characteristics were significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher in the selenium-supplemented group as compared to others. However, the Se + Vit. E group showed significantly lower testicular weights, while the control and Vit. E groups had similar ($p > 0.05$) epididymis lengths.

Effects of selenium and vitamin E supplementation on spermatozoa characteristics of Yankasa rams

Table 3 summarizes the effects of selenium (Se), vitamin E (Vit. E), and their combination (Se + Vit. E) on various spermatozoa characteristics in Yankasa rams. All parameters measured differ ($p < 0.05$) significantly across the treatment groups except for normal, bent tail, and detached head. The percentage of spermatozoa with proximal droplets was significantly ($p < 0.05$) lower in the Se + Vit. E group compared to others. The lowest ($p < 0.05$) percentage of sperm with coiled tails is observed in the Vit. E group, and the highest ($p < 0.05$) is in the selenium-supplemented group. The percentage of microcephalic spermatozoa is significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) in the control group compared to treated animals.

Effects of selenium and vitamin E supplementation on catecholamines of Yankasa rams

Effects of selenium (Se), vitamin E (Vit. E), and their combination (Se + Vit. E) on catecholamines in Yankasa rams are presented in **Table 4**. All parameters measured are statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) across the treatment groups.

Table 2: Testicular characteristic of Yankasa rams supplemented with selenium and vitamin E

Testis characteristics	Treatments				p
	Control	Se	Se + Vit. E	Vit. E	
Testicular length (cm)	9.17 ± 0.74 ^b	10.30 ± 0.95 ^a	4.48 ± 0.45 ^{cd}	5.25 ± 0.50 ^c	0.001
Testicular weight (g)	219.3 ± 20.8 ^{ab}	228.7 ± 22.5 ^a	71.3 ± 6.8 ^c	120.8 ± 11.5 ^b	0.001
Testicular breadth (cm)	3.80 ± 0.40	2.30 ± 0.23	1.33 ± 0.14	1.90 ± 0.20	0.090
Vas deferens length (cm)	16.39 ± 1.65	17.40 ± 1.70	15.70 ± 1.60	13.50 ± 1.35	0.430
Epididymis length (cm)	17.10 ± 1.65 ^c	28.80 ± 2.90 ^a	20.50 ± 2.00 ^b	15.56 ± 1.55 ^c	0.001

a, b, c: means bearing different superscripts within the same row differ (P<0.05)

Table 3: Spermatozoa characteristics of Yankasa rams supplemented with selenium and vitamin E

Sperm characteristics (%)	Treatments				P-value
	Control	Se	Se + Vit. E	Vit. E	
Normal	69.9 ± 2.03	84.3 ± 2.0	70.3 ± 13.89	81.3 ± 2.0	0.082
Bent Tail	14.8 ± 11.43	3.3 ± 0.1	25.4 ± 19.97	3.5 ± 0.1	0.131
Detached head	7.0 ± 5.37	3.3 ± 0.1	1.13 ± 1.96	4.0 ± 1.0	0.180
Proximal Droplet	4.13 ± 0.12 ^b	0.8 ± 0.01 ^c	0.3 ± 0.52 ^b	9.5 ± 0.1 ^a	0.000
Coiled Tail	2.7 ± 2.52 ^b	8.3 ± 0.1 ^a	3.7 ± 3.87 ^b	1.3 ± 0.1 ^{bc}	0.028
Microcephalic	1.5 ± 0.1 ^a	0.0 ± 0.0 ^c	0.0 ± 0.0 ^c	0.4 ± 0.1 ^b	0.019

a, b, c: means bearing different superscripts within the same row differ (P<0.05)

Rams in the Se + Vit. E group had higher (P<0.05) dopamine compared with rams in the control and Vit. E groups but similar to the Se group. The highest (p < 0.05) adrenaline level is observed in the selenium-supplemented group, which is similar (p > 0.05) to the control group, and the lowest is in the Se + vit. E group. Rams in the control group had higher (P<0.05) noradrenaline levels as compared to others. The lowest value was recorded in rams receiving Vit. E.

DISCUSSION

Testicular characteristics are key indicators of reproductive potential in male animals, with parameters such as testicular size, weight, and epididymal length playing crucial roles in sperm production and fertility. In this study, the effects of selenium (Se) and vitamin E supplementation on testicular morphology in Yankasa rams were evaluated. The findings indicate significant variations in testicular length, weight, and epididymal length among the treatment groups, suggesting the effect of these antioxidants on testicular development and function. Testicular length significantly varied among treatments, with the highest value recorded in the

selenium-supplemented group. Selenium plays a vital role in testicular development by modulating oxidative stress and supporting the function of Sertoli and Leydig cells, which are crucial for testicular growth and spermatogenesis (Zhang et al., 2020). The increased testicular length and weight in the selenium-only group aligns with previous studies in cocks, where selenium supplementation enhanced testicular size and reproductive efficiency (Li et al., 2020). Ahsan et al. (2014) demonstrated that Se deficiency, or low selenium status, is related to numerous reproductive disorders, including abnormal testicular morphology (Varlamova, 2016), and decreased testicle weights (Li et al., 2020).

Testicular weight is directly associated with sperm-producing capacity, as larger testes contain more seminiferous tubules and a higher sperm reservoir (Toe et al., 2000). The increased weight in the selenium group is consistent with previous findings in sheep and goats, where selenium supplementation improved testicular growth by enhancing steroidogenesis and reducing lipid peroxidation (Shi et al., 2018).

Table 4: Catecholamines levels of Yankasa rams supplemented with selenium and vitamin E

Parameters	Treatments				P-value
	Control	Se	Vit. E	Se + Vit. E	
Dopamine (pg/mL)	130 ± 43.14 ^b	140.7 ± 10.69 ^{ab}	97.7 ± 11.72 ^b	174.7 ± 8.96 ^a	0.024
Adrenaline (ng/mL)	1.153 ± 0.13 ^a	1.197 ± 0.08 ^a	0.45 ± 0.05 ^c	0.88 ± 0.12 ^b	<0.000
Noradrenaline (ng/mL)	2.0 ± 0.10 ^a	0.637 ± 0.05 ^b	0.163 ± 0.11 ^c	0.65 ± 0.06 ^b	<0.000

a, b, c: means bearing different superscripts within the same row differ (P<0.05)

The significantly lower testicular weight observed in the Se + Vit. E and vitamin E groups may not only suggest a lack of synergy between selenium and vitamin E in promoting testicular development but could also reflect possible dose-dependent effects of vitamin E, nutrient antagonism, or differences in bioavailability between dietary and parenteral routes of supplementation. This may explain the discrepancy with **Elbaz and Razek (2019)**, who reported synergistic effects of selenium and vitamin E supplementation on testicular metrics. Epididymis length showed significant variations, with the selenium-supplemented group having the longest epididymis and the vitamin E-only and control groups recording the shortest lengths. The epididymis is essential for sperm maturation, storage, and transport (**James et al., 2020**). A longer epididymis is often associated with improved sperm quality due to extended sperm transit time, allowing for better sperm maturation (**Fernandez et al., 2008**). The significantly longer epididymis in the selenium group supports previous studies that showed selenium supplementation enhances epididymal length, function, and sperm quality (**Elbaz and Razek, 2019**). However, the reduced epididymis length in the vitamin E-only group suggests that while vitamin E has antioxidant properties, it may not directly contribute to epididymal growth. Similar results were reported in bulls, where vitamin E did not significantly influence epididymal structure (**Mahmoud et al., 2013**).

Spermatozoa morphology is a key indicator of male fertility, with structural abnormalities affecting sperm motility, viability, and overall reproductive performance (**Menkveld et al., 2010**). The results demonstrated variations in sperm abnormalities, particularly in proximal droplets, coiled tails, and microcephalic sperm cells, highlighting the potential role of these

antioxidants in improving sperm quality. The percentage of normal spermatozoa ranged from 69.9% (control) to 84.3% (Se). However, rams supplemented with selenium and vitamin E alone exhibited higher normal sperm counts (84.3% and 81.3%, respectively), indicating a potential improvement in sperm integrity. Similarly, in assessing the effect of housing and season on semen morphological abnormalities of Uda rams, **Aljameel et al. (2021)** reported a similar percentage of normal sperm cells as a result of reduced oxidative stress.

Selenium is a key component of selenoproteins such as glutathione peroxidase, which protect spermatozoa from oxidative damage (**Xiao et al., 2021**). Previous studies have demonstrated that dietary Se supplementation enhances sperm morphology and motility in rams (**Wang et al., 2021**). Similarly, vitamin E is a potent lipid-soluble antioxidant that preserves sperm membrane integrity by reducing lipid peroxidation (**Sabetian et al., 2021**). The combined supplementation of Se and vitamin E has been shown to have synergistic effects on reproductive performance and sperm quality (**Musa et al., 2018**). In sheep, combined supplementation improved sperm morphology compared to individual supplementation (**Sabetian et al., 2021**). The observed increase in normal spermatozoa in Se- and vitamin E-supplemented groups supports these findings, suggesting improved testicular function and reduced oxidative stress.

The percentage of bent-tail spermatozoa was highest in the control group and lower in the treated groups. Although not statistically significant, this trend suggests that antioxidant supplementation may reduce structural sperm defects. Bent tails are often associated with oxidative damage or abnormal epididymal maturation

(Lindemann and Lesich, 2016). Selenium and vitamin E supplementation have been shown to enhance sperm membrane stability, reducing tail defects (Alonge et al., 2019). The decreased bent-tail percentages observed in the supplemented groups align with studies in rams and bulls where selenium and vitamin E improved sperm morphology and reduced abnormalities (Sabetian et al., 2021). Detached head abnormalities were reduced in the Se + Vit. E group compared to the control. Although also not statistically significant, the observed reduction in the Se + Vit. E group suggests a potential protective effect against sperm head detachment. Sperm head detachment can result from oxidative stress (Wang et al., 2025), mutation (Avidor-Reiss et al., 2020), infections, or testicular dysfunction (Zhu et al., 2019). Selenium plays a vital role in spermatogenesis, particularly in protecting sperm DNA from oxidative fragmentation (Li et al., 2023). The present findings support earlier studies that reported improved sperm head morphology following vitamin E supplementation (Moslemi and Tavanbakhsh, 2011).

Proximal droplets indicate sperm immaturity and are commonly associated with oxidative stress or testicular dysfunction (Cooper, 2011). The significant reduction in proximal droplets in selenium-supplemented groups is consistent with the role of selenium in sperm maturation (Kommissrud et al., 2005). Studies have shown that selenium enhances epididymal sperm maturation (Noblanc et al., 2011), reducing the incidence of retained cytoplasmic droplets (Xiao et al., 2021). However, the high percentage in the vitamin E-only group suggests that vitamin E alone may not be sufficient for optimal sperm maturation. Coiled tail defects are often linked to testicular or epididymal dysfunction and excessive oxidative stress. The higher incidence in the selenium-only group is contradictory to findings in humans, where selenium reduced sperm tail defects (Maiorino et al., 1999). This discrepancy could be due to species differences, dosage variations, or interactions between selenium and other trace minerals.

Microcephalic (small-headed) spermatozoa was highest in the control group (1.5%) and significantly lower in all supplemented groups. Microcephaly is a severe abnormality linked to defective spermatogenesis, possibly resulting from stress, nutritional deficiencies,

or diseases (Auger et al., 2016). Selenium plays a crucial role in testicular function, with deficiencies linked to sperm morphological defects (Alonge et al., 2019). The complete absence of microcephalic sperm in the Se and Se + Vit. E groups supports the hypothesis that selenium supplementation improves sperm maturation.

Catecholamines, including dopamine, adrenaline, and noradrenaline, play a crucial role in stress responses, metabolic regulation, and cardiovascular function in ruminant functions (Khalil et al., 2024). The increase in dopamine levels in the vitamin E group is consistent with previous studies demonstrating that vitamin E has neuroprotective properties and may enhance dopaminergic activity. For instance, supplementation with antioxidants showed increased dopamine turnover and reduced stress in the brain, suggesting an anti-stress-mediated neuroprotective effect (Bellavite, 2023). Conversely, the significant reduction in dopamine levels in the Se + vitamin E group suggests a possible interaction between selenium and vitamin E that affects dopaminergic metabolism.

Adrenaline was higher in the Se group and control than the Se + vitamin E group. These results suggest that selenium and vitamin E, when combined, may suppress adrenaline secretion, possibly through antioxidant effects that mitigate stress-induced adrenal activation. The reduction in adrenaline with Se and vitamin E supplementation aligns with previous studies (Kadim et al., 2006; Chulayo et al., 2012) on oxidative stress and adrenal function in ruminants. Research on heat-stressed goats supplemented with Se and vitamin E found decreased adrenaline levels, attributed to reduced oxidative damage in the adrenal medulla (Kannan et al., 2003). Furthermore, selenium's role in glutathione peroxidase activity helps neutralize reactive oxygen species (ROS), thereby dampening the stress response and lowering adrenaline secretion (Li et al., 2023). Interestingly, the individual supplementation of selenium or vitamin E alone did reduce adrenaline levels compared to the control but as combined effects, suggesting that their combined effect is synergistic rather than additive. This is consistent with findings in dairy cows, where combined selenium and vitamin E supplementation reduced stress biomarkers more

effectively than either supplement alone (**Mokhber-Dezfouli et al., 2008**).

Noradrenaline levels were highest in the control group (2.0 ng/mL) and significantly lower in the treated groups. The drastic reduction in the Se + vitamin E group suggests that these antioxidants effectively attenuate sympathetic nervous system activity. The observed reduction in noradrenaline is consistent with studies in livestock where antioxidant supplementation reduced stress-induced catecholamine release. Serum plasma total antioxidant status was greatest in sheep receiving Se and vitamin E supplements in heat-stressed sheep (**Alhidary et al., 2015**). These results indicate that dietary supplementation with Se and vitamin E reduces the adverse effects of a high heat load. The authors suggested that these antioxidants protect against stress-induced lipid peroxidation in the adrenal medulla, thereby preventing excessive catecholamine release.

Furthermore, the reduced noradrenaline levels may be attributed to improved oxidative balance, as selenium is a key component of glutathione peroxidase, which detoxifies ROS and prevents excessive adrenal stimulation (**Li et al., 2023**). High secretion of catecholamine because of elevated stress impairs testicular function and epididymal sperm transport (**Frungieri and Mayerhofer, 2024; Urra et al., 2014**). Elevated oxidative stress has been associated with increased catecholamine levels, creating a feedback loop that aggravates reproductive dysfunction (**Guerriero et al., 2018**).

CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates that selenium (Se) alone improved testicular development, while Se + Vit. E combined optimized sperm morphology, including proximal droplets and eliminating microcephalic sperm. However, animals receiving supplements had reduced catecholamine secretion (adrenaline and noradrenaline). These findings provide practical strategies to enhance *Yankasa* ram productivity in tropical smallholder systems.

AUTHORS CONTRIBUTION

A.I. Bukar conceived and designed the study, conducted the experiment, collected the data, and drafted the manuscript. **S.A. Maigandi** supervised the research design and data interpretation. **M.S. Yahaya** contributed to experimental design, statistical analysis, and manuscript revision. **K.M. Ajameel** assisted with laboratory analyses and data validation. All authors read and approved the final version of the manuscript.

ETHICAL APPROVAL

All experimental procedures involving animals were conducted in accordance with the guidelines for the care and use of laboratory animals as outlined by the National Research Council (2011). Ethical clearance was obtained from the Animal Ethics Committee of Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, and all efforts were made to minimize animal discomfort.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

FUNDING STATEMENT

This research received partial financial support from the Academic Staff Union of Universities (**ASUU**) of Nigeria PhD Research Grant, 2024.

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